

VIS Guide for IN-HABIThon

Detailed description of the Visionary and Integrated Solutions (VIS) adopted within the IN-HABIT framework to work on the IN-HABIThon

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Introduction to VIS in IN-HABIT

Within the IN-HABIT framework, we refer to VIS (*Visionary and Integrated Solutions*) as those interventions, actions, and tools that are co-designed to improve quality of life, inclusion, and well-being in urban communities. They are **visionary** because they address real challenges with innovative ideas, and **integrated** because they connect different dimensions (social, environmental, cultural, and economic) and are developed in coordination with other projects and stakeholders.

In each pilot city, VIS have been created through co-design processes with the local community and ecosystem, and can take two forms:

- **Soft VIS:** activities, programmes, and social, cultural, or training dynamics that create change in people and strengthen social cohesion.
- **Hard VIS:** physical interventions, infrastructure, or material elements that transform spaces and enable new uses.

VIS are **living solutions** that constantly evolve. They emerge from needs identified at a specific moment, but their development and use depend on changing factors: community engagement, resource availability, environmental conditions, or new opportunities. Therefore, when working on them, the current reality may not exactly match the description in this guide: they may have been expanded, modified, or be at a different stage than originally planned.

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For the IN-HABIThon, we have made a selection of VIS and propose choosing one of them and improving it by applying the Design for Change (DFC) methodology. This will allow us to dream big, rethink and strengthen existing solutions from the community's perspective, exploring how they can become more inclusive, sustainable, and meaningful for those who use them. Through the Feel–Imagine–Do–Evaluate–Share stages, we will identify opportunities, propose concrete changes, and design small prototypes or actions to boost their positive impact. Once the IN-HABIThon has been completed, compare the solutions proposed by IN-HABIT.

To use this guide, we have organised the VIS by city. We have also included a table at the beginning of each section so that you can select the objective that best suits the challenge you want to tackle. You can also group several VIS together in the same challenge if they have similar objectives. After selecting the VIS from the table, look for it below along with its detailed description for further information.

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VIS at Córdoba (Table)

Objectives	Name	Type
Inter-institutional coordination, empowerment, political advocacy	Palmeras Committee	Soft
Personal empowerment, creative expression, inclusion	De dentro pa' fuera (From Inside Out)	Soft
Cohesion, neighborhood pride, positive visibility	Bailar mi barrio (Dance My Neighborhood)	Soft
Environmental care, shared responsibility, institutional pressure	Community Activities	Soft
Accessible communication, transparency, participation	Newsletter	Soft
Access to culture, neighborhood-city connection	FLORA Event	Soft
Environmental education, sustainable habits	SADECO Workshops	Soft
Green employment, healthy leisure time, environmental awareness	Gardening Trainings	Soft
Creative expression, visibility, digital inclusion	Entreplanos	Soft
Digital literacy, innovation, youth participation	Artificial Intelligence Workshops	Soft

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Communication, cohesion, empowerment	Radio Program	Soft
Digital inclusion, quality of life improvement	New Technologies Workshops	Soft
Women's empowerment, fighting stigma, healthy habits	Perol Gourmet	Soft
Recreation, social cohesion, reclaiming public space	Picnic Area	Hard
Urban revitalization, coexistence, cultural inclusion	Central Plaza Renovation	Hard
Thermal comfort, environmental improvement, cohesion	Renaturalization of Patios and Cantarranas Stream	Hard
Wellbeing, practical skills, social inclusion	Shelter for Homeless People	Hard

Soft VIS

Gender, Diversity, Inclusion, and Social Innovation

1. Palmeras Committee

A stable platform made up of representatives from associations, organisations and local residents to coordinate joint actions. It meets regularly to discuss problems, propose solutions and channel the voice of the community to institutions. It has served as a space for cohesion, negotiation and collective decision-making, strengthening community leadership.

Objectives: inter-institutional coordination, empowerment, and political advocacy.

2. De dentro pa' fuera (Inside Out)

Community theatre workshop that draws on the real-life experiences of participants to create collective works. The process fosters self-esteem, emotional expression and creativity,

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generating artistic products with great symbolic significance. The results have been presented at open cultural events, reinforcing a sense of pride.

Objectives: personal empowerment, creative expression, inclusion.

3. Dancing in my neighbourhood

Community dance project where residents and professional artists co-create choreographies inspired by neighborhood life. Public performances have served as a tool for visibility and positive advocacy. Dance has become a means to strengthen collective identity and open dialogues with the rest of the city.

Objectives: cohesion, neighborhood pride, positive visibility.

4. Community Activities

Community initiatives such as collective clean-ups and beautification of public spaces. These serve to strengthen shared responsibility and draw institutional attention to the neighbourhood. They have demonstrated the community's capacity for self-organisation and collective care.

Objectives: care for the environment, shared responsibility, and institutional pressure.

5. Newsletter

A printed monthly bulletin delivered by hand to keep neighbors informed about activities, progress, and opportunities. Its accessible and approachable format ensures it reaches people who do not use social media or digital channels. It has contributed to transparency and participation.

Objectives: accessible communication, transparency, participation.

Environment and Sustainability

6. FLORA Event

Active participation of Palmeras residents in Córdoba's international floral art festival. This experience has brought culture and contemporary art closer to an audience that normally does not access these circuits. It has also fostered connections with artists and broadened the perception of belonging to the city.

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Objectives: access to culture, neighborhood–city connection.

7. SADECO Workshops

Hands-on workshops on recycling, composting, and reuse, complemented by visits to Córdoba’s waste treatment plant. Participants have acquired knowledge and skills for sustainable waste management at home, encouraging habit change and environmental awareness.

Objectives: environmental education, sustainable habits.

8. Gardening Trainings

Training courses in gardening for residents, focused on the maintenance of green spaces and urban gardens. They have combined theory and practice to promote employability and better use of public spaces. Many participants have applied what they learned in subsequent community interventions.

Objectives: green employment, healthy use of free time, environmental awareness.

Infrastructure, Technology, and Digitalization

9. Entreplanos

Participation in the international short-film competition recorded with mobile phones, with a special mention for urban inclusivity. Workshops were organized for migrant youth and older women, who created short films about life in Palmeras. The videos reached thousands of views and highlighted local stories with international reach.

Objectives: creative expression, visibility, digital inclusion.

10. Artificial Intelligence Workshops

Workshops for teenagers on AI tools applied to health, well-being, and co-design of urban solutions. Led with support from researchers at the University of Granada, they introduced advanced digital skills in a context with low technological access. Young participants generated innovative proposals for the neighborhood.

Objectives: digital literacy, innovation, youth participation.

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11. Progama de Radio

A monthly program on the community station “Palmeras, tu voz se escucha” where residents share experiences, music, and news. It is the second most listened-to program on the station and has served as a platform for positive initiatives. Its participatory format reinforces belonging and cohesion.

Objectives: communication, cohesion, empowerment.

12. New Technologies Workshops

Practical training on the use of new technologies to improve health, well-being, and accessibility. Developed with local associations, they have opened the door to digital inclusion for marginalized groups. They have demonstrated how technology can be a tool to improve quality of life.

Objectives: digital inclusion, improved quality of life.

Food Culture and Gastronomic Events

13. Perol Gourmet

A large-scale culinary event co-created by renowned chefs and neighborhood women to reinterpret the traditional Córdoba “perol.” More than 350 people attended in person, and 1.7 million saw it through national media. The event has combated stigma, supported small local businesses, and strengthened community pride.

Objectives: female empowerment, fight against stigma, healthy habits.

Hard VIS

1. Picnic Area

Recovery of a degraded natural area next to the Cantarranas stream, turned into a picnic zone with granite tables and benches. Designed in workshops with residents and executed by a company from another vulnerable neighborhood. It has not suffered vandalism in over two years and has become a meeting and event space.

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Objectives: recreation, social cohesion, reclaiming public space.

2. Renovation of the Central Square

Complete remodeling of Las Palmeras' central square with anti-vandalism furniture, green areas, and inclusive cultural spaces. Elements were included to respect local traditions such as bonfires. Since its inauguration, the square has become the epicenter of celebrations and community activities.

Objectives: urban revitalization, coexistence, cultural inclusion.

3. Renaturalization of Las Palmeras Patios and Cantarranas Stream

Planting of over 300 trees and 1,200 shrubs in courtyards and along the stream, with the creation of a pedestrian walkway. Co-design workshops involved residents in choosing species and designing furniture. It has improved habitability, thermal comfort, and connection with nature.

Objectives: thermal comfort, environmental improvement, cohesion.

4. Homeless shelter

Creation of an urban garden and therapeutic garden in a shelter for homeless individuals, managed by the residents themselves. Activities include cultivation, maintenance, and building elements such as insect hotels and composters. It has generated therapeutic benefits, practical skills, and a sense of belonging.

Objectives: well-being, practical skills, social inclusion.

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VIS at Riga (Table)

Objectives	Name	Type
Social inclusion, community cohesion, fight against discrimination	Social Events	Soft
Universal access to culture, strengthened sense of belonging, citizen participation	Cultural Events	Soft
Empowerment, capacity building, socio-labor integration	Educational Events	Soft
Environmental awareness, waste reduction, public space improvement	Environmental Events	Soft
Circular economy, support for small producers, waste reduction	Economic/Sustainable Trade Events	Soft
Urban revitalization, accessibility, social cohesion	Transformation of the Outdoor Market	Hard
Healthy eating, social cohesion, cultural exchange	Community Kitchen	Hard
Efficient waste management, environmental awareness, food waste reduction	Eco-Island	Hard

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Soft VIS

Gender, Diversity, Inclusion, and Social Innovation

1. Social Events

Interactive activities such as celebrations, competitions, creative workshops, community meals, and multicultural gatherings that bring together people of all ages and backgrounds. Developed in collaboration with merchants, artists, cultural institutions, and NGOs, these events encourage active participation and shared learning. They make use of infrastructures such as the community stage and community kitchen to create safe and inclusive spaces.

Objectives: social inclusion, community cohesion, fight against discrimination.

2. Cultural Events

Concerts, theater, folk dances, and other public artistic expressions organized with both professional and amateur groups. These events preserve and promote cultural heritage, strengthen local identity, and encourage active participation. They are mainly held in the renovated outdoor market, which now serves as a community cultural center.

Objectives: universal access to culture, strengthening sense of belonging, civic participation.

3. Educational Events

Workshops on cooking, gardening sessions, language classes, business training, and other activities that provide practical knowledge. Targeted at specific groups such as youth, families, older people, ethnic minorities, or refugees. Conducted with the support of experts and professionals, combining theoretical and practical learning.

Objectives: empowerment, skills development, socio-labor integration.

Environment and Sustainability

4. Environmental Events

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Initiatives such as recycling, composting, object repair workshops, and gardening activities in the community garden. They promote sustainable habits and encourage active involvement in environmental stewardship.

Objectives: environmental awareness, waste reduction, improvement of public space.

5. Economic / Sustainable Trade Events

Weekly and monthly second-hand and vintage markets that promote reuse, repair, and waste reduction. In addition to boosting the local economy, they foster the circular economy and conscious consumption.

Objectives: circular economy, support for small producers, waste reduction.

Hard VIS

6. Transformation of the Outdoor Market

Comprehensive renovation of the outdoor market square to create a multifunctional space with green areas, a community stage, a greenhouse, and a garden. The result of a co-design process with residents, associations, and authorities, balancing different visions and needs. It has enhanced the development of social, cultural, and educational events.

Objectives: urban revitalization, accessibility, social cohesion.

7. Community kitchen

Equipped space on the first floor of the market for culinary, educational, and intercultural activities. It enables recipe sharing, promotes healthy eating habits, and hosts inclusive events for the whole community.

Objectives: healthy eating, social cohesion, cultural exchange.

8. Eco-Island

Dedicated area for selective waste collection, with staff who advise and educate vendors and visitors. It has reduced management costs by about €600 per month and improved the

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cleanliness and safety of the environment. Includes plant, book, and textile exchange points, as well as water fountains and last-minute food products to prevent waste.

Objectives: efficient waste management, environmental awareness, reduction of food waste.

VIS at Lucca (Table)

Objectives	Name	Type
Emotional wellbeing, cognitive stimulation, social interaction, non-pharmacological therapy	Animal-Assisted Interventions (AAI)	Soft
Protection of the human-animal bond, support for vulnerable groups, shared responsibility	Pet Care Services	Soft
Playful learning, social integration, understanding of animal welfare	“City Pets” Board Game	Soft
Responsible tourism, accessible information, promotion of inclusive services	Pet-Friendly Services Map	Soft
Social inclusion, strengthening the human-animal bond, public space improvement, universal accessibility	Animal Lines	Hard
Universal accessibility, animal welfare, social cohesion	Accessible Relational Areas	Hard
Accessible information, inclusive tourism, active mobility	Interactive Map of Animal Lines	Hard

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Citizen science, environmental monitoring, biodiversity awareness

LEKO Biodiversity Sensors

Hard

Soft VIS

1. Animal-assisted interventions (AAI)

Program implemented in two care homes for older adults to improve the well-being of residents, including those with dementia. Developed with specialist associations, the municipality, the University of Pisa, and care home staff, delivering 90 sessions over nine months.

Objectives: emotional well-being, cognitive stimulation, social interaction, non-pharmacological therapy.

2. Pet care services

Initiative to support vulnerable individuals with companion animals in temporary situations of need. Offers three types of services: in-home care, walks with the owner, and walks without the owner, including veterinary transport.

Objectives: protecting the human-animal bond, support for vulnerable groups, shared responsibility.

3. City Pets board game

Play-based tool for learning about animal behavior, needs, and coexistence in urban environments. Tested with students and the general public before being used in schools and events. Access the game on the IN-HABIT website.

Objectives: playful learning, promotion of social integration, understanding animal welfare.

4. Map of pet-friendly services

Co-created map showcasing services and places adapted for people with pets, based on surveys and joint work with the tourism sector.

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Objectives: responsible tourism, accessible information, promotion of inclusive services.

Hard VIS

Gender, Diversity, Inclusion and Social Innovation

1. Animal Lines

Pedestrian route connecting the historic center with peri-urban areas, integrating green spaces such as the historic walls and the “Spalti.” Includes two relational areas accessible for people and pets, designed to foster the human-animal bond and social inclusion. The design was participatory, incorporating accessibility, animal welfare, and community use needs.

Objectives: social inclusion, promotion of the human-animal bond, improvement of public space, universal accessibility.

2. Accessible relational areas

Spaces adapted for people with disabilities, equipped for animal-assisted interventions and sports activities with pets. Their location was chosen for accessibility and proximity to the Animal Lines route, with fountains, rest areas, and durable furniture.

Objectives: universal accessibility, animal welfare, social cohesion.

3. Interactive map of Animal Lines

Tool in development showing routes of different difficulty and accessibility, along with relational areas, fountains, rest areas, pet-friendly businesses, and cultural/natural points of interest. It will be integrated into the project’s app for easy use.

Objectives: accessible information, inclusive tourism, active mobility.

5. LEKO biodiversity sensors

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Installation of two sensors to monitor biodiversity health in the Lucca River Park, in collaboration with BIRDZ and MNHN in France.

Objectives: citizen science, environmental monitoring, biodiversity awareness.

VIS at Nitra (Table)

Objectives	Name	Type
Social inclusion, accessible cultural leisure, community strengthening	Sunday Chills	Soft
Environmental education, responsible consumption, community pride	KOZAfest	Soft
Social integration, inclusive use of public space, shared tradition	Pumpkin Parade	Soft
Cultural preservation, refugee integration, intercultural coexistence	Ivana Kupala Festival	Soft
Youth leadership, climate action, citizen participation	Be the Change	Soft
Food self-sufficiency, environmental education, local economy	Community Garden Workshops & Markets	Soft
Creative expression, inclusion, community development	Artistic & Cultural Workshops	Soft
Active living, inclusion through sport, health	Sports Activities in Hidepark	Soft

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Sustainable mobility, practical skills, equitable access to transport	Bike-Sharing System	Soft
Social cohesion, food use, cultural integration, year-round usability	Community Kitchen “Yurt”	Hard
Skills development, community production, cultural activation	Community Workshop “DIY Café”	Hard
Practical environmental education, sustainable urban farming, community cohesion	KOZA Community Garden	Hard
Educational inclusion, community integration, outdoor learning	Revitalization of Dražovce Schoolyard	Hard
Inclusive use of public space, citizen creativity, social interaction	Multifunctional & Reversible Urban Furniture	Hard
Coexistence, active recreation, equitable access to green areas	Dražovce Picnic Meadow	Hard
Physical and mental wellbeing, urban biodiversity, adaptive use of spaces with legal restrictions	Zelokvet Experimental Picnic Meadow and Corridor Meadows	Hard

Soft VIS

Gender, Diversity, Inclusion, and Social Innovation

1. Sunday Chills

Summer event series in Hidepark featuring music, theater, creative workshops, and intercultural activities such as language cafés and vegan dinners. Engages families, youth, older adults, and

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migrant and refugee communities.

Objectives: social inclusion, accessible cultural leisure, community strengthening.

2. KOZAfest

Annual festival celebrating the community garden harvest with recycling workshops, local markets, talks, and educational activities.

Objectives: environmental education, responsible consumption, community pride.

3. Pumpkin Parade

Autumn street event with pumpkin carving, music, and community soup, designed to bring together the majority population and the Roma community in a shared space.

Objectives: social integration, inclusive use of public space, shared tradition.

4. Ivana Kupala Festival

Traditional Ukrainian celebration with bonfire, music, and dance, organized together with the migrant and refugee community.

Objectives: cultural preservation, refugee integration, intercultural coexistence.

5. Be the Change

Youth-led climate awareness event organized by a 16-year-old student with technical and logistical project support. Included talks, recycling workshops, and a “Messages for the Future” wall.

Objectives: youth leadership, climate action, civic participation.

6. Community garden workshops and markets

Training in composting, permaculture, and ecological pest control, alongside KOZA markets for selling surplus and local products.

Objectives: food self-sufficiency, environmental education, local economy.

7. Artistic and cultural workshops

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Include participatory photography for Ukrainians and people with disabilities, painting, percussion, recycled fashion, and collaborative art residencies.

Objectives: creative expression, inclusion, community development.

8. Sports activities at Hidepark

Yoga, Zumba, training sessions, and Hidepark's Children's Football Club, with equipment acquired for community use.

Objectives: active living, inclusion through sport, health.

9. Bike-sharing system

Refurbishment of donated bicycles, free or low-cost rentals, and beginner repair workshops.

Objectives: sustainable mobility, practical skills, equitable transport access.

Hard VIS

Gender, Diversity, Inclusion, and Social Innovation

1. Yurt Community Kitchen

Mobile, reversible space installed in a refurbished Mongolian yurt, restored with volunteers and reused materials. Functions as a community kitchen for transforming garden surplus into collective meals and as a venue for workshops, talks, and neighborhood meetings—even in winter thanks to its stove.

Objectives: social cohesion, food use, cultural integration, year-round usability.

2. “DIY Café” Community Workshop

Housed in a recycled shipping container, it combines a production space (woodwork, metal, upholstery, graphic arts) with a mobile stage and vertical greenery, turning it into a cultural venue. Co-designed with the community and partly funded through an accelerator program, it promotes circular economy and technical training.

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Objectives: skills development, community production, cultural activation.

3. KOZA community garden

Expanded by 575 m² with new cultivation, education, and relaxation areas. Includes a garden workshop, chicken sanctuary, aquatic plant pond, rebuilt pergola, and furniture made from waste materials. Regular training promotes permaculture and urban biodiversity.

Objectives: practical environmental education, sustainable urban agriculture, community cohesion.

4. Revitalisation of the school playground in Dražovce

Transformation of a segregated school space into an interactive outdoor classroom with green areas, play furniture, and sports spaces. Jointly designed by Roma and majority students to encourage inclusion and shared use.

Objectives: educational inclusion, community integration, outdoor learning.

5. Multifunctional and reversible street furniture

Designed with biophilic principles and vandal-resistance, using fallen wood, recycled plastic, and textile concrete. Includes benches, modular structures, and participatory public art that can be relocated and reconfigured by users. Created with refugee and differently-abled participants.

Objectives: inclusive use of public space, citizen creativity, promotion of interaction.

6. Dražovce picnic meadow

Green space with tables and rest areas, designed as a meeting point for residents of different communities.

Objectives: coexistence, active recreation, equitable access to green areas.

7. Zelokvet experimental picnic meadow and meadows along the corridor

Innovative intervention in a flood-prone area with therapeutic meadows, an acupuncture park, terrain modulation for healthy play, and countersunk flood-resistant barbecues. Includes planting of 161 trees and educational activities such as BioBlitz and floral workshops.

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Objectives: physical and mental well-being, urban biodiversity, adaptive use of legally restricted spaces.

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